

Supplementary Figure 1: Cell depth in μm of WM (blue, left of dotted line) and GM (red, right of dotted line) enriched microglia after treatment with LPS, myelin or myelin+LPS. Black dots represent data from individual microglia, bars represent the mean and \pm SEM.

Supplementary Figure 2: Representative lightmicroscopical image of primary mixed glial cells cultured in ibidi μ -dish with grid used for indentation. Microglia are identified by IBA-1 immunoreactivity (pink), astrocytes are identified by GFAP immunoreactivity (brown). Scalebar = 250 μ m.

Supplementary Figure 3: Graph depicting mRNA levels of *Aif-1* and *Gfap* in WM (blue) and GM (red) derived mixed glial cell cultures. Black dots represent data from 3 individual cultures, bars represent the mean and +/- SEM. We observed no statistical differences in the mRNA expression of *Aif-1* or *Gfap* between conditions (ns).